

EFFECTS OF HUMIDITY ON THE FRACTURE BEHAVIOR OF POLYMERIC MATRIX MATERIAL UNDER DYNAMIC LOADING

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ABSTRACT

The effects of water sorption on the dynamic fracture of notched polymeric matrix materials were examined. The materials used were vinyl ester resin and poly-methyl methacrylate (PMMA). Two sets of samples were used: the first set was conditioned in an 11% relative humidity (RH) environment using a saturated salt solution (Lithium Chloride), and the second set was immersed in distilled water. Samples were kept in their respective environments for 43 days and subjected to stress pulses generated by the impact of a projectile launched from an air gun. The dynamic loading conditions were kept constant to analyse the effect of water content on the dynamic fracture initiation of both sample sets. It was observed that the fracture toughness and crack-tip speed of samples with higher water content showed no significant difference for both materials compared to dry samples.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymeric materials are often utilized in naval and aircraft applications as the matrix component of composite materials. This means they are exposed to outdoor environments, in which conditions may vary significantly and material properties could change due to this. In order to use these materials in such environments, it is important to understand how environmental conditions affect their performance under different loading conditions. Many uses for these materials may involve exposure to high loading rates in liquid environments, such as in seawater for naval purposes, or in varying humidity levels, such as an aircraft traveling through various climates. This topic must be further considered as many practical applications depend on knowledge of the behavior of polymers under high strain rate loading conditions and hostile environments.

Even though composite materials are the ones to be used in marine or naval applications, any changes in subjected loading amplitude and loading rate can affect the properties of the polymer matrix, which could in turn influence the fracture toughness of the composite. Thus, the mechanical properties and rate sensitivity of the polymer matrix directly determine the rate sensitivities of the polymer composite [1]. It is important that the matrix component materials are well understood and characterized for the loading conditions to which they can be subjected.

Dynamic loading is a widely used technique to determine the dynamic properties of a material. One method to generate dynamic loading is by impact, which generates stress waves that travel through a solid. Initially, the stress wave created through the impact travels as a compressive pulse. Once the compressive pulse impinges the free rear surface of the sample, a rarefaction wave is created and reflected as a tensile pulse that returns the sample to ambient pressure [2]. The amplitude of the tensile pulse depends on the impedance mismatch at the interface of the free end and the fluid to which it is exposed. Fracture occurs if the tensile pulse exceeds the tensile strength of the material [3].

The effect of the environment in material fracture is referred to as environmental stress cracking, which is one of the most common causes of unexpected brittle failure of polymeric materials. There has been considerable work performed on the fracture behavior of PMMA in liquid environments for tensile testing at low strain rates [4–9]. Experimental results show that for strain rates of $10^{-3} - 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$

the fracture behavior of PMMA changes as water uptake increases. For instance, Hamouda [6] found that water sorption leads to the improvement of flexibility, ductility, and fracture toughness of PMMA, but also, a reduction in hardness and stiffness for tensile tests in samples with levels of water absorption of up to 0.8%. Bokoi et al. [10] showed that the toughness of PMMA changed with water content for samples subjected to static tensile testing. The critical stress intensity factor (SIF), K_{IC} , increased from 0.9 MPa \sqrt{m} for dry samples to 1.2 MPa \sqrt{m} for samples with a water content of up to 1.3 wt.%. As water absorption increases and higher strain rates are applied, the tensile strength of PMMA will be influenced by two competing effects: a reduction due to water sorption and an increase due to higher strain rates applied. Therefore, results for lower loading rates should not be generalized to higher loading rates without previous experimentation.

Additionally, the mechanics of water sorption in vinyl ester are well understood for samples subjected to accelerated aging tests (e.g. hygrothermal aging) or natural ageing tests (e.g. room temperature water immersion) [11-13] and it is commonly accepted that the low water sorption capability of vinyl ester resin – ranging values from 0.2 wt.% to 0.8 wt.% depending on the conditioning temperature and duration – is due to few ester groups available in its structure for hydrolysis to occur [14-16]. The effect of water content on the mechanical properties of vinyl ester neat resin is an active research area and it has shown greater retention of mechanical properties over commonly used resins for marine applications (e.g., polyester). These studies also included the interaction of vinyl ester as a matrix in composite materials with various water contents for different loading conditions [16-21]. The mode-I critical stress intensity factor (SIF) has been previously studied in experiments conducted at a strain rate of 10^{-3} s $^{-1}$ on single-edge-notch bend tests [22]. The values obtained are within the range of $K_{IC}=0.7-1.7$ MPa \sqrt{m} . The variation in the value of K_{IC} is a result of the various compositions of the vinyl ester resin utilized by different research groups. Also, it was reported that the fracture toughness of the material does not seem to have significant loading rate sensitivity for strain rates of $10^{-3}-10^{-4}$ s $^{-1}$ [23].

However, to the best of the authors' knowledge, these studies have not included the effects of water content on the dynamic fracture initiation of vinyl ester or PMMA when subjected to strain rates at or above 10^2 s $^{-1}$. This study examined the effects of sorbed water and humidity exposure on mode-I crack propagation in vinyl ester neat resin and PMMA specimens. Samples were subjected to equal amplitude tensile stress pulses by edge-on ballistic loading reaching strain rates of 10^2 s $^{-1}$. The relationship between water content and dynamic fracture initiation is discussed in this study. The optical method of transmitted caustics, with a high-speed camera, was used in these experiments.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

A spherical steel projectile launched from an air gun was utilized to impact the short edge of rectangular vinyl ester samples. Loading conditions were monitored using strain gauges, and fracture initiation was visualized using the method of caustics. The samples used in this study had the same geometry as used in [24]. Specimens used had a thickness of 3.3 ± 0.09 mm and dimensions 300 mm \times 40 mm. A 10 mm long and 0.152 mm wide notch was sawn at half length of the sample. This type of geometry allowed for a pure mode-I crack to occur when a tensile pulse was applied. Due to its cross-sectional aspect ratio (12:1), three-dimensional effects could be ignored, and it could be assumed that the wave traveling through the specimen due to impact was a plane-stress wave [24]. The materials used were commercially available PMMA and the vinyl ester resin sheets were provided by collaborators at the NSWC Carderock Division.

A total of 20 specimens for each material were divided into two different sets corresponding to their respective environment exposure: (1) 11% relative humidity (RH) and (2) distilled water. The first set of samples investigated the effects on fracture behavior due to exposure to an 11% RH environment. This environment was obtained by using a Lithium Chloride saturated solution at 25°C [6]. The amount of salt used and the solution intensity are shown in Table 1. The saturated solution was placed in airtight containers with the specimens positioned in holders above the solution. The

relative humidity value in the closed container, generated by the vapor pressure from the solution, was frequently monitored using a thermo-hygrometer (PTH 8707).

Solution	RH [%]	Used amount [g]	Intensity [g/ml]
<i>LiCl</i>	11	2505	0.835

Table 1: Salt Solution Specifications

The second set of samples was used to investigate the effects on dynamic fracture behavior due to immersion in distilled water. The results presented in this study correspond to samples conditioned in these environments for 43 days at 25°C because water sorption rates significantly decreased after this. Samples were exposed to 11% RH and distilled water environments to simulate the opposite humidity level conditions to which the materials could be exposed. The weight change was frequently monitored using a weight scale (ML4002E/03, Mettler Toledo) to obtain the water content as a function of time. The weight change was calculated using the following equation:

$$C = 100 \times (W_f - W_i) / W_i \quad (1)$$

where C (wt%) is the water content, W_i is the weight of a sample before immersion, and W_f is the weight of the sample containing sorbed water. Figure 1 shows the weight measurements as a function of conditioning time. It was observed that the water content of the specimens changed and the rate of change decreased with time. As expected, the water content was higher for samples immersed in distilled water compared to the ones exposed to 11% RH. After 43 days of exposure there was an average water content differential of 0.49 wt% (0.26 g) between samples conditioned at different environments for vinyl ester samples and an average water content differential of 1.12 wt% (0.52 g) for PMMA samples.

Figure 1: Water absorption with time for: (a) Vinyl ester (reproduced from [25]), (b) PMMA. (■) samples immersed in distilled water; (x) samples exposed to 11% RH

A challenge of dynamic loading experiments is to obtain repeatable loading conditions so that the results from consecutive experiments can be compared. The setup consists of a pressurized air gun, a visualization system, a test section, and a catcher box to contain the experimental samples during and after impact, see Figure 2. The method of transmitted caustics was used to observe the crack propagation behavior of the samples. The velocity of the projectile depends on the pressure in the air gun reservoir at the time of launch. Further details on the air gun, the launching mechanism and the velocity sensor are presented in detail in [25, 26]. In order to record the impulsive loading and ensure repeatability of loading conditions between successive experiments, a 3.5 mm long strain gauge (Micro-Measurements EA-13-125BZ-350/LE) was glued to each sample 50 mm behind the notch post-conditioning.

Figure 2: Experimental Setup: (1) Catcher box with samples inside, (2) Gas gun, (3) Light Source, (4) Flat Mirror, (5) Concave Mirror, (6) High-speed camera

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The strain responses from the strain gauges attached to the samples were used to observe the impact conditions. The strain gauge responses correspond to an impact velocity of 31.9 ± 0.40 m/s and an average maximum strain of $\epsilon_{max} = 4106 \pm 145$ μ strain for vinyl ester samples, shown in Figure 3; and the strain gauge signals for PMMA samples correspond to an impact velocity of 37.8 ± 0.40 m/s, which generated a maximum strain of $\epsilon_{max} = 2480 \pm 255$ μ strain, shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Average strain response for 12 vinyl ester resin samples (reproduced from [25])

Figure 4: Average strain response for 10 PMMA samples

The method of caustics was then used to quantify the dynamic fracture initiation and initial propagation stages for the various samples. The SIF was calculated by measuring the transverse diameter of the caustic curves as the crack propagated. Figure 5 and 6 show a sequence of caustic images for vinyl ester and PMMA samples, respectively. To post-process these images, any optical distortions were removed using a virtual grid with known points, which were mapped onto the recorded images. Then, the location and the diameter of each caustic were measured at the points of the curve where the highest intensity pixels were located.

Figure 5: Crack propagation sequence for vinyl ester resin using the method of caustic (13 μs between images) [25]

Figure 6: Crack propagation sequence for PMMA using the method of caustic (13 μ s between images)

The results obtained for crack velocity and SIF for vinyl ester samples exposed to 11% RH and distilled water are shown in Figure 7 and 8, respectively. Even though samples had been conditioned in opposite humidity level environments for 43 days, no significant difference was found in the initial stages of crack propagation. Crack-tip speed was calculated from the crack-tip displacement, and velocities up to 454 m/s were recorded. It can be seen that the critical SIF is similar for both sets of samples with an approximate value of $K_{IC} = 1.5 \text{ MPa}\sqrt{\text{m}}$. This value falls within the range obtained at lower strain rates ($\sim 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$), which agrees with the low loading rate sensitivity of the mode-I fracture toughness of vinyl ester resin reported by [23]. Also, it is inferred from this that water has a marginal effect on the fracture toughness of vinyl ester resin for strain rates of 10^2 s^{-1} . Also, both sets of vinyl ester samples show similar SIF for the initial stages of crack propagation.

Figure 7: Average crack speed for vinyl ester resin (reproduced from [25]).
 (○) samples immersed in distilled water; (▲) samples exposed to 11% RH
 Uncertainty for each data point is represented by marker size

Figure 8: Initial and propagating SIF for vinyl ester resin (reproduced from [25]).
(○) samples immersed in distilled water; (▲) samples exposed to 11% RH
Uncertainty for each data point is represented by marker size

The results obtained for crack velocity and SIF for PMMA samples exposed to 11% RH and distilled water are shown in Figure 9 and 10, respectively. A slight difference in crack speed can be observed; cracks propagated faster as the water content increased. However, the crack-tip speed converged to the same value as the crack continued to propagate. The main difference in the crack-tip speed was observed only in the initial segment of the crack propagation. The results for the SIF show that the fracture toughness of the material does not vary significantly with water content. The average critical SIF obtained was 2 MPa√m for both cases. As it can be seen, both cases follow the same trend and show a clearly defined critical SIF, identified in Figure 10 as the stage where the crack begins to propagate. The results reported in this study show that when the strain rate is increased, the toughening effect of water content does not seem to prevail, and the effects of the strain rate dominate the fracture behavior of PMMA. These findings do not agree with the results by [6–10], who observed differences in the fracture behavior of samples whose immersion times varied from a few minutes to several months when subjected to strain rates of $10^{-3} - 10^{-8} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Thus, results obtained in this study showed that water content is not a dominant mechanism at strain rates on the order of 10^2 s^{-1} .

Figure 9: Average crack speed for PMMA.
(○) samples immersed in distilled water; (▲) samples exposed to 11% RH.
Uncertainty for each data point is represented by marker size

Figure 10: Initial and propagating SIF for PMMA.
 (○) samples immersed in distilled water; (▲) samples exposed to 11% RH
 Uncertainty for each data point is represented by marker size

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the dynamic fracture behavior of vinyl ester neat resin and PMMA samples conditioned in two environments yielding different water uptake in the samples was investigated. The results can be concluded as follows:

- The experimental setup design has shown to yield repeatable results for samples impacted in room conditions. Impact velocities had a variation of ± 0.82 m/s for all 40 experiments performed, and strain responses showed that loading conditions were similar.
- The mode-I critical SIF value of PMMA obtained at 10^2 s⁻¹ was similar for samples with different water contents. The value obtained for both sets of samples for the mode-I critical SIF was $K_{IC}=2$ MPa√m. This differs from the results presented by Bokoi et al. [10], who showed there was a significant variation in the fracture toughness of the material for different water contents. Additionally, the crack propagation and speed of PMMA for different water contents showed a similar behavior, regardless how the conditioning was performed. Results obtained in this study showed that water content is not a dominant mechanism in the fracture behavior of PMMA at strain rates on the order of 10^2 s⁻¹.
- Water content had a negligible effect on the fracture toughness of vinyl ester neat resin for the strain rate at which these tests were conducted (10^2 s⁻¹). Comparisons were made by calculating the SIF on both sets of samples and both showed similar behavior in the initial stage of crack propagation. The value obtained for the mode-I critical SIF, $K_{IC}=1.5$ MPa√m, agrees with what was reported in previous studies, $K_{IC}=0.7-1.7$ MPa√m, at strain rates on the order of 10^{-3} s⁻¹. Also, it implies that fracture toughness of the material does not seem to be rate sensitive up to a strain rate of 10^2 s⁻¹.

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